

The role of patenting in emerging renewable energy technologies: The case of wave energy technology development

Barry, C.A.; Conlon, P.; Tavares, A; and Ringwood, J.V.

Abstract—This study examines the role of intellectual property (IP) protection in the development of wave energy technologies amid the transition to a low-carbon energy system. It evaluates patents as indicators of innovation and their inherent limitations, such as long development timelines, high costs, and expiration risks. Alternative IP protection strategies are also considered, including licensing agreements and trade secrets. The study compares patent-driven IP protection strategy with open innovation strategies, questioning whether patents foster, or hinder, progress within the sector. The paper contrasts wave energy patenting trends with more mature renewable energy modalities, highlighting unique challenges, such as the lack of a design archetype. Using international patent reports, data from patent office databases, and bibliometric analysis, the study identifies trends in wave energy technology development. The study assesses whether patents encourage or obstruct innovation, and argues that patent data, combined with bibliometric analysis, can inform development strategies and pragmatic policy developments. Ultimately, the study recommends assessing trends in wave energy technology development through a combination of patent registration data and academic publication data to provide information to policymakers, developers, and investors interested in wave energy technology.

Index Terms—Patenting, wave energy, open innovation, patent trends, intellectual property strategies, bibliometric analysis ...

I. INTRODUCTION

THE integration of renewable energy technologies in transitioning to a low-carbon energy system cannot be overstated. The optimal renewable energy system will comprise a variety of modalities to ensure security of supply. The energy sector will reach net zero emissions only if there is a significant and concerted global push to accelerate innovation [1]. Wave energy technology can make up a significant part of the renewable energy mix [2] and help to serve this global need. The advantages of wave power are significant, and include an energy density up to 10 times that of solar or wind at a latitude of 15° N [3]. This is in addition

to high availability in certain areas, complementarity with other renewable resources, and good relative predictability [4]. Furthermore, international, European, and national carbon emission targets, including offshore renewable energy targets, have ensured that renewable energy development has been enshrined in national statute books, providing additional motivation to policy makers to support technology development [5].

Despite this potential, wave energy technology development lags behind its more mature renewable energy counterparts, such as Solar Photo Voltaic (PV) and onshore wind energy, and requires additional support to take it beyond the technology readiness midpoint [6]. Intellectual Property (IP) protection plays a role in fostering innovation and protecting technologies from competitors. One of the rationales for patent registration, as an IP protection strategy, is that patents stimulate technological development and promote competition, by creating a financial motivation for invention, in exchange for the disclosure of the invention to the public [7]. Organisations can use patents as an asset to attract investment, or as a means to dissuade competitors from activity in the same area. From a government's perspective, patents are important in helping to understand the source of new technologies, and can help to fund their development [8]. Patent statistics provide indicators to measure and examine trends in innovation, commercialisation, and knowledge transfer across international markets [9], as governments require a detailed analysis of technological innovation trends to design appropriate policies to promote renewable energy [10].

One of the main functions of the patent system is the dissemination of technical information. Patent information is a valuable source of technical, commercial, and legal knowledge that can be used for scientific purposes, and as a basis to stimulate the adaptation and improvement of the technology described in patent documents [7]. Patents also provide insights into changes in technology trends and identify new actors in the area through patent trend analysis [9].

This study focuses on the role and effectiveness of patents in the wave energy technology development sector. The research explores strategies used by wave energy technology developers for the protection of innovations, and examines their efficacy. The study provides information for interested actors and policy advisors on the *status quo* in wave energy technology

© 2025 European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference. This paper has been subjected to single-blind peer review.

This work was supported by MaREI, the Research Ireland Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine, Ireland (grant No. 12/RC/2302_P2) and through the European Research Council (ERC) under EU Horizon funding (Grant Agreement No. 101147456 – SHY)

Barry, C.A. and Ringwood, J.V. are with the Centre for Ocean Energy Research and Conlon, P, is with the Commercialisation Office all at Maynooth University, Maynooth, Co. Kildare (e-mail: CarrieAnne.Barry@mu.ie, Tavares, A is with University College Cork.

Digital Object Identifier:
<https://doi.org/10.36688/ewtec-2025-883>

development. The study also explores challenges in relation to patent registration, including long development timelines and patent expiration, as well as costs considered prohibitive by some organisations. Attempting to analyse trends by looking at patent behaviour, may be difficult due to the lack of a dominant wave energy converter (WEC) design, and the unwillingness of some wave energy developers to patent. Alternative IP strategies, specifically trade secrets and the impact on licensing agreements, are considered. This study addresses the following questions:

- 1) Do patents drive or hinder innovation in wave energy?
- 2) Are patents a viable metric to gauge wave energy technology developments?
- 3) Is there an IP protection strategy best suited to wave energy technology development?

Following the introduction, Section 2 discusses IP protection in relation to renewable energy technologies, and challenges facing patent registration for wave energy technology developers. Section 3 describes alternative IP strategies, while Section 4 provides a case study. Section 5 examines trends in wave energy patenting, while Section 6 compares trends in wave energy technology academic publishing to trends in patent registration. Sections 7 and 8 provide discussion and conclusions.

II. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Patent registration has been considered a valuable form of IP protection for many years; indeed, the first patent in relation to wave energy was registered in 1799. A patent translates technology into legal writing in order to protect technological advances. A patent confers the right to exclude others from making, using, selling, or importing the patented invention, in a particular jurisdiction. This 'industrial property' can be assigned, transferred, licensed, or used by its owner. [11].

In order for an invention to be held to be patentable, it must have industrial applicability, the invention must not exist in the state of the art, including through the inventor's own publications; and there must be an observable inventive step. Patents give the inventor control over their technology, in that they are legally entitled to object to someone's use of the invention. Patents also provide assurance to potential investors.

An early wave energy patent of 1873, (Fig. 1), describes improvements made to a floating buoy type WEC. It distinguishes between what was known and what the inventor now claims the improvements are. The protection granted, only includes the improved elements (in this case the piston and floating buoy combination). The requirements of industrial applicability, novelty, and an inventive step are satisfied.

John Flaherty, from leading Irish IP Solicitors firm FRKelly, gives some insight into the patenting process. He clarifies that the art of patent registration is in the description of the patent. The description cannot be too general or too broad, and what is described in the claim must be comprehensive, but must not include the prior

Fig. 1. Patent US138474A. Buckner, C. Wave Powers 1873 [12]

art. When drafting a patent, the closest prior art must be found, and the description must show the novel steps and advantages. A balance must be achieved between showing inventiveness, and not publicising details unnecessarily.

The steps for patent registration are similar in many countries. In Ireland, for example, they are as follows:

- 1) Evaluation: Patent attorneys assess corporate risks, benefits, and existing art.
- 2) First filing: Applications are submitted with specifications, claims, and drawings [13]. From the date of first filing, the applicant is entitled to claim the priority date of that application.
- 3) Examination: The IP Controller reviews compliance, and upon approval, the patent is published and takes effect [14].

The process takes approximately 22 months.

A number of sanctions are available to plaintiffs whose patent has been found to be infringed. The infringing party can be subject to an injunction, a legal order to stop the offending action. This may include mandatory licensing and/or damages. Alternatively, compensatory monetary remedies may be awarded, based on a calculation of profits or a calculation of potential royalties. Other potential sanctions include delivery-up (handing over all infringing goods), or destruction of infringing goods, a recall order, publication of the decision and declaration of infringement [13].

Patent data serves as an indicator of innovation due

to its long availability, verification by patent examiners, and easy access [15]. The extended data period is valuable for linking trends to policy or legislative changes [16]. However, patents are sometimes filed for defensive reasons, such as maintaining a competitive advantage, or meeting funder requirements, rather than to protect innovation. For example, Research Ireland mandates open access publishing, while Enterprise Ireland favours IP protection through spin-outs and patenting. Inventors may also patent to attract investment, or satisfy shareholders, particularly in publicly listed companies.

A. Limitations of patents

Patents can be costly, and decisions must be taken about the countries in which to register patents. The application process can be time-consuming, and legal language can be difficult to understand. The following are some of the challenges faced by those who choose patent registration as an IP protection strategy.

1) *Lack of case law*: There is very little patent infringement case law and, despite relatively similar legislation in different jurisdictions, outcomes in different jurisdictions can differ widely, largely due to local procedural differences [17].

2) *Visibility*: Patents are publicly available, and as such, it can be preferable to delay the release of the invention until the device is commercially viable, unless the inventor is actively seeking investment.

3) *Lack of dominant design*: WEC systems generally consist of a hull; a power take-off (PTO) system, by which mechanical energy is converted into electrical energy; and a control system to safeguard overall operations, maximise energy [18].

In addition to the complexity of wave energy conversion systems, there are a wide variety of designs, and no particular design has reached a technology readiness level (TRL) that facilitates large-scale commercialisation [19]. There is little consensus on the number of distinct WEC designs, although international bodies such as the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), describes the major device types [18]. The lack of a dominant design makes it challenging to secure innovation through patent applications, as the degree of novelty becomes harder to define [20]. Moreover, multiple competing designs can exert an influence on patenting efforts, complicating proprietary rights, and hindering the commercialisation efforts of new technologies [21]. This level of technological and market uncertainty, can contribute to the deceleration of investments in WEC systems development [22]. Therefore, the lack of a standardised design archetype presents significant barriers to both innovation and patenting activity.

4) *Cost*: The cost of a patent filing has 2 components: the attorney costs (between €3000 and €10000 for a preliminary application with, for example, the UK Patent Office or the European Patent Office (EPO)). Subsequent progress into the Patent Cooperation Treaty phase costs €5000-€7000 in attorney fees. Nationalisation requires both attorney (in addition to any transla-

tion cost required), and official fees for each jurisdiction.

To limit spend, organisations may decide to seek protection in countries, according to key markets by sales volume, competitor location, manufacturing, or R&D location.

III. AN ILLUSTRATIVE ACCOUNT

In 2012, The Guardian reported a burglary at Pelamis Wave Power in Scotland, during which several laptops were allegedly stolen shortly after a visit by a Chinese delegation [23]. Two years later, a structurally similar wave energy device—the Hailong (Dragon) 1—emerged in China.

Fig. 2. Pelamis Wave Energy Converter and Hailong (Dragon) 1. Source: The Guardian newspaper, (2012)

Although observers noted visual and mechanical similarities, such as hinged joints and deployment mechanisms, these do not constitute evidence of IP infringement. The Chinese Embassy denied any copying, stating that the Hailong was independently developed [24]. Pelamis, which ceased operations in 2014, after investments totalling approximately £95 million, had not secured patent protection in China, and no legal action was pursued.

This case is included not as verified infringement, but as a journalistic account cited to illustrate the challenges of international IP protection in wave energy, not least due to the lack of case law in the area. It highlights perceived risks, but should be interpreted critically, given the lack of conclusive technical or legal validation.

In a closely related area, recent patent infringement litigation involving wind turbines for offshore arrays [17] was brought before the US District Court, in which a Boston federal judge, in 2022, banned General Electric (GE) from making and selling its Haliade-X wind turbines in the United States, after a jury found in June of the same year, that the turbines infringed a patent owned by rival Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S (Siemens). Judge William Young found that Siemens was entitled to the ban because it suffered irreparable harm, including a significant loss of market share to GE due to the infringement. However, Young allowed GE to continue making and operating the turbine for existing projects off the coasts of Massachusetts and New Jersey with royalty payments to Siemens,

allowing GE to “design around” the patents. A jury had found that Siemens was entitled to royalties of \$30,000 per megawatt produced from GE’s infringing turbines. The infringement involved patent 8575776, relating to the enhanced performance of the turbine by improving the operation of cooling and maintenance.

An interesting element to this judgment was that Judge Williams permitted the operation of the existing turbines, due to the effect that decommissioning them would have on climate targets and employment in the New Jersey area, should the company be forced to cease trading.

However, when Siemens took the dispute to the United Kingdom High Court, they lost. Judge Richard Meade found that Siemens, which had sued GE claiming that the Haliade-X infringed its European patent related to the use of bearings in rotor hubs for wind turbines, did not have a valid patent. Even if the patent was held to be valid, Meade found that “neither the fully assembled Haliade-X nor its hub” fell within the scope of Siemens’ patent [25].

With this level of uncertainty, it is unsurprising that there is scant litigation in the area, and demonstrates that the decision as to whether or not to patent is nuanced and complicated.

IV. DEVELOPING IP STRATEGIES

A trade secret can often be considered an alternative to patent registration as an IP protection strategy. A trade secret, is a piece of information that derives economic value from not generally being known to those outside the organisation, and is the subject of reasonable efforts to maintain its secrecy [26]. Trade secrets do not suffer from complex procedures and long timelines, and are less costly than patents. Trade secrets may be protected in law by the doctrine of inevitable disclosure, i.e. when it is inevitable that an employee would divulge trade secrets, whether deliberately or not, they may be prevented from joining another company in the absence of a non-compete agreement. Therefore, an employer-friendly trade regime may limit innovation [26]. In general, when considering whether to patent or maintain trade secrecy, wave energy technology developers have to assess the trade-off between information disclosure, and maintaining a temporary monopoly.

Patents may be preferred over secrecy, if there is a higher risk of imitation. If the details revealed in the patent registration reveal nothing more than might be gleaned through careful observation of the invention, there is more incentive to patent. For process innovations, trade secrets are often preferred, as they are generally more difficult to reverse engineer. In the case of wave energy, the WEC hull could be seen to be more easily replicated, than the device controller for example.

The complexity of the patenting procedure, as well as the timeline involved, described in Section 2, is off-putting for many inventors. The Intellectual Property Action Plan 2020 [27] recognises and attempts to address this challenge through a unitary patent

Fig. 3. Evolution of Renewable Energy Patents (2000-2023) - Data derived from the EPO PATSTAT 2023 Autumn edition on Climate Change Mitigation Technologies (Y02) classification [33]

system [28]. However, a lack of harmonisation among jurisdictions complicates this endeavour.

The most significant reason that start-ups choose trade secrecy over patenting is the cost [29]. Crass [30] finds that, for single innovations, a combination of trade secrecy and patenting provides the highest sales, when IP protection is high, where there is high technological uncertainty, high novelty, and requires financial investment. Patent applications are mainly undertaken by innovators that develop new (physical) goods. In contrast, service and process innovations show low patenting rates [31].

V. PATENTING TRENDS IN OCEAN ENERGY

An overview of international patenting activity in the ocean energy area from international reports and literature follows. According to the EU Commission Clean Energy Technology Observatory November 2022 report [32], between 2010 and 2019, 3,561 patent applications involving ocean energy were submitted globally, with 1677 granted, 710 of which were high value (in terms of market impact and economic significance). China was responsible for 49% of applications. Inventors from the EU were responsible for 12% of applications, with 73% of submissions made by companies. The EU submitted most high value inventions (34%). According to the report [32], in terms of international protection, inventions originating from the EU account for 18% of the total international inventions. Around 15% of the EU inventions are protected internationally while, for China, only 1% of inventions are internationally protected.

Trends in patenting, in renewable energies in general, show that the number of high value inventions is steadily decreasing in the European Union, and increasing in China. Moreover, solar PV, and PV thermal hybrid technologies are both increasing at the highest rate, and make up the largest portion of patent filings (Fig. 3). The rate of patenting in fossils fuels has remained stagnant since 2001 [1]. The dominant activity of solar PV patenting suggests that solar PV

Fig. 4. WEC patenting trends (2008-2020)

technologies are extensively used in the marketplace, marine energy is shown to be at a deployment, demonstration, or R&D phase, and therefore shows relatively less activity.

According to WIPO [7], wave and tidal (combined) make up 3% of patent filings from 2010-2019. In general, WIPO find that patent filings for renewable energies have increased at a rate of 10% per year, starting in 1990. Countries that have policies that support renewable energy development, such as feed-in tariffs, have more patent filings. Germany is a market leader in the fields of solar and wind power and has enshrined policy support in their 2000 Renewable Energy Sources Act (Fig.3).

In order to delve more deeply into the relationship that wave energy technology has with patenting, as a form of IP protection, and as a potential indicator of innovation, this study uses the PATSTAT database [34] to construct patent counts using the International Patent Classification System [?], a hierarchy of codes at different levels. The PTSTAT platform corresponds to the EPO register of European patents. The patent publication period from 2008-2020 is considered. Data mining and curation through keywords is conducted, the keywords being derived from a comprehensive literature review of technological developments (this approach was used, for example, in an International Energy Agency (IEA) report. [35].

Figure 4 shows that WEC patenting activity saw a sharp increase between 2010 and 2012. These dates are based on the publication date of the patent, which usually comes 1-2 years after first filing. This would put commercial interest in WECs as coincidental with a period of governmental and international organisational interest, in the integration of renewable energy, at a time where nearly all international events, such as G8 summits and UN General Assemblies, placed climate change mitigation at the top of their respective agendas [36]. Pazhouhan [37] looks at wave and tidal publication dates over a longer period, and found that global patenting rates increased from 2000 onward.

Table 1 shows patent registration trends, observed from the PTSTAT database, that were published between 2008 and 2020.

There is significant variation in the type of inventions

being patented in this area. Most patents relate to the device itself, arguably the simplest element to replicate through observation. 3% of patents were for PTO devices, and 1.5% were for controllers, while 46% of patents published were for methodologies or models. This study also analyses the number of patents that

Fig. 5. WEC patents by type (2008-2020)

were withdrawn. This makes up a significant minority of patents (31%). A withdrawal indicates that the application has been withdrawn at the applicant's request. This occurs when the applicant decides not to pursue the patent application and to withdraw it from the examination process. There are several reasons why an applicant may withdraw a patent application:

- Change in strategy: The applicant may change plans or business strategy, and determine that it no longer makes sense to continue the patent application.
- Lack of likelihood of success: The applicant may discover, during the examination process, that the chances of success in obtaining a patent are low. In such cases, the applicant may decide to withdraw the application to save time and resources.
- Cost Reasons: Proceeding with a patent application may involve significant costs, especially if additional examination requirements, or third party oppositions, arise. The applicant may then decide to withdraw the application for financial reasons.

The advantage of withdrawing a patent application, is that secrecy may be maintained.

It is noteworthy to consider the originators of the patent filings (Table 1). This is expressed in Fig 5, and shows that companies are, by far, most likely to register patents over individuals or academics. This may indicate the greater need for companies to hold a patent portfolio, in order to attract private investment however, this does not indicate actual numbers of companies as a percentage of applicants, as companies are much more likely to hold a portfolio of patents than individuals or universities. In Germany, of the 33 WEC patents registered during the period 2008-2020, 14 were registered by Robert Bosch GmbH (although this company has more recently turned their attention to hydrogen electrolysis). Another example is Russia,

TABLE I
NUMBER OF PATENTS PUBLISHED ACCORDING TO PTSTAT DATABASE (2008-2020)

Country	Patents published	Withdrawn	Company	University	Individual
Australia	13	7	11	0	2
Austria	1	0	0	0	1
Azerbaijan	1	1	0	0	1
Belgium	1	0	1	0	1
Brazil	2	2	1	0	1
Canada	1	0	0	1	0
Chile	3	2	0	0	3
China	9	0	3	0	6
Denmark	17	5	15	0	2
Egypt	1	0	0	0	1
Finland	26	3	23	1	2
France	22	6	13	0	9
Germany	33	13	23	0	10
India	2	0	0	0	2
Ireland	9	3	8	0	1
Israel	3	2	1	0	2
Italy	18	2	13	1	4
Japan	14	3	6	5	3
Korea	17	9	11	3	3
Mexico	1	1	0	0	1
Moldova	1	0	0	0	1
Netherlands	7	2	5	0	2
Norway	20	7	13	1	6
Poland	1	0	0	0	1
Russia	3	0	0	0	3
Saudi Arabia	1	0	1	0	0
Serbia	1	0	0	0	1
Singapore	1	0	1	0	0
South Africa	1	1	1	0	0
Spain	9	5	4	0	5
Sweden	33	7	33	0	0
Switzerland	3	0	3	0	0
Taiwan	5	2	0	1	4
Tunisia	1	1	0	0	1
Turkey	3	0	3	0	0
UK	58	23	44	1	13
US	45	12	35	1	9
Total	387	119	272	9	94

where 3 patents were registered, all by the same individual, who also registered the only patent in the area of wave energy technology from Serbia.

VI. BIBLIOMETRICS

A bibliometric analysis of academic publications may provide an alternative or complementary indicator of activity within the wave energy sector. Bibliometric analyses can provide an overview of the state of the art in a field, highlight gaps in the sector, and may provide an opportunity to derive novel ideas and to position contributions within a field. A bibliometric review, can provide evidence and mapping of scientific knowledge in a field [38]. Bibliometric analysis can also summarise the evolution and current state of research and emerging research fronts, and can give a global perspective [37].

Fig. 6. Wave energy patents by organisation type (2008-2020)

Eligibility criteria for contributions to high-ranking academic journals have some commonalities with patents. In order to be academically publishable, the concept must be novel, and for technical academic journals, must show some applicability, and funding agencies such as the EU, require open access publication. Indeed, some journal articles are required to go further than the requirement of patent examinations, in that the concept must be validated by robust, peer-reviewed, simulations and/or modelling. Publishing in academic journals nullifies eligibility to patent, unless the patent application is made before the academic paper is made public.

Scopus [39] is a database of peer-reviewed literature, that includes scientific journals, books, and conference proceedings. The authors select Scopus as a data source for the bibliometric analysis in this study, due to its coverage, citation data from a wide range of sources, a wide range of metrics to evaluate research impact, and a significant amount of open access content.

The analysis uses keyword search terms with Boolean operators (combinations), from 2008 to 2020 to facilitate comparison with the patent registration data in this study.

Fig. 7. Number of wave energy converter papers per year (2008-2020)

Figure 7 shows the number of wave energy converter articles per year from 2008-2020. As the trend for wave energy technology patent registration has declined, the number of wave energy converter published articles has increased as shown in Figure 8. This corresponds to the stage of development of the technology, the technology shows significant innovation, but has not reached commercial maturity.

Figure 9 ranks wave energy publication authors by numbers of articles written over the period 2008-2020. The authors listed are all based at academic institutions. The relative proliferation of papers by individuals is not replicated in patent registrations, possibly due to cost, given that most of the cost for academic publications in the area is generally covered by funding agencies, by ‘transformational’ agreements between universities and publishing companies, or due to the commercial organisation choosing a different form of IP protection, such as trade secrecy.

The highest numbers of patent registrations during the period are from the UK, the US, Sweden, Germany,

Fig. 8. Trend comparison between WEC articles published and wave energy technology patents registered with EPO (2008-2020)

Fig. 9. Top wave energy publications by author (2008-2020)

Fig. 10. Wave energy converter publications - top performing countries (2008-2020)

and Finland. China, the top performer in terms of academic publications in the area, during the period, ranks 13th, with Spain and Ireland. Spain and Ireland perform significantly better in terms of the number of academic papers produced.

In general, observing bibliometric data, alongside patent registration trends, gives a more complete picture of technology development and shows where innovation is derived from. Analysing academic literature can provide information on non-patented inventions, as well as highlighting new areas of interest, and may be useful when considering where hubs of innovation activity can be found.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Patentability and innovation in wave energy

Patent applications predominantly arise from innovations that develop new physical goods, whereas service and process innovations exhibit significantly lower patenting rates [31]. Collaboration by inventors with universities has been shown to increase the likelihood of patenting, as academic institutions often engage in formalised IP protection to secure funding and investment. However, not all patents are indicative of genuine innovation or technological progress; in some cases, patents are filed strategically to block competitors rather than to commercialise new inventions. Generally, funding in the area of wave energy technology is seen to be relatively accessible at early technology readiness levels (TRL) [6] (1 to 3), but falls away at TRL 4 and over, when costs increase exponentially, and the need for IP protection becomes more important as innovators seek external investor funding.

Patent filing is a critical decision for technology developers, often driven by a balance between cost, time, and the stage of technological development, as well as the requirement to maintain secrecy. This decision is further complicated by competing pressures, such as the ‘publish or perish’ culture in academia, versus the need for intellectual property protection to attract investors. The uncertainty surrounding future market potential, can also influence whether developers choose to patent their innovations or rely on alternative IP protection strategies such as trade secrets.

B. The role of appropriability regimes and complementary assets

Klevatorick et al. [40] highlight that disruptive technologies can gain market traction when appropriability regimes (the regimes that govern an innovator’s ability to capture the profits from an innovation) fail, and firms instead secure complementary assets, such as manufacturing, distribution, and supply chain capabilities. This approach has been taken by wave energy technology company CorPower Ocean [41], arguably to secure against the risk of appropriability regime failure, as they have developed mobile assembly units at port facilities, reducing reliance on fixed manufacturing sites, and enabling more agile deployment. Having available test facilities, a streamlined consenting system, and suitable infrastructure are essential for development in the area [42], and will contribute to an improved appropriability regime.

One of the challenges in assessing patenting trends in wave energy is the lack of information on non-patented inventions. Bibliometric analyses can partially address this gap, by identifying scientific publications that disclose innovations outside the patenting system. Additionally, the ability to reverse-engineer a component or system influences whether developers choose to patent an innovation, or not. Klevatorick [40] suggests that digitalisation has shifted the locus of innovation, with key system functionality increasingly dictated by software and control systems, rather than hardware. This is particularly relevant in wave energy, where the

controller plays a pivotal role in device performance, but that has yet to impact patenting trend data significantly.

C. Evaluating the usefulness of patent trend data

Patent trend data offer several advantages as an indicator of innovation: the novelty of inventions is evaluated by patent examiners, the data are accessible through platforms such as the European Patent Office (EPO), and longitudinal analysis can reveal technological shifts over time [31]. However, patents are not always the most effective protection mechanism. Maurseth et al, [43] argue that lead times and secrecy often provide better protection than formal patents, particularly in industries where knowledge is tacit and difficult to codify. Pisano [44], in his review of Teece’s “Profiting from Innovation”, [45], further notes that not all technological advancements receive the same level of IP protection. For example, open-source software innovations, may struggle to secure patents, while hardware innovations can be more easily protected. Additionally, there are cases where patented technologies fail to capture economic returns, as seen with IBM’s early computing patents, and Bowmar’s calculator [46], the first handheld LED display calculator. Bowmar relied heavily on Texas Instruments for components and failed to secure strong patents, enabling Texas Instruments and other competitors to enter the market with cheaper, more advanced models, ultimately driving Bowmar into liquidation.

D. The innovation ecosystem

The wave energy sector operates within a broad innovation ecosystem, which includes academia as generators of knowledge, industry as generators of technology, and government as supporters of growth [47]. The role of government, is essential in emerging renewable energy technologies, and should extend to financial support for IP protection for organisations in this area of national and global importance. The need for such support can be gleaned by observing the difference in numbers of published academic articles, compared to the number of patents published in the same period. That is not to say that academic research should not be supported. In fact, Mansfield [48] found that 11% of new industrial products and 9% of new processes could not have been developed without substantial delay and cost, in the absence of recent academic research. Additionally, organisations, that have an extensive patent portfolio in the area of wave energy, tend to be large companies, with greater access to finance, such as Bosch GmbH, rather than the SMEs that are more commonly seen in the wave energy sector. Generally, funding in the area of wave energy technology is seen to be relatively accessible at early TRLs (1 to 3) [6], but falls away at higher TRLs, when costs increase exponentially, and the need for IP protection becomes more important as innovators seek external investor funding.

Patents can foster technology transfer, facilitating the sale or licencing of protected technology, whereas trade

secrets may adversely effect knowledge transfer [49]. This is particularly relevant in the case of renewable energy technology, given that the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) discusses the urgent need to encourage licencing for technology transfer to developing countries [50]. Providing funding for patent registration, if that is the preferred protection strategy, may also facilitate this imperative as firms are confident to disclose technology when negotiating a licensing contract, where patents offer a delineation of technological assets, combined with the assurance of market exclusivity.

By addressing these considerations, governments and funding agencies can create a more effective innovation ecosystem that supports both scientific discovery and the commercialisation of wave energy technologies.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the value of bibliometric analysis in complementing patent data, in the assessment of innovation trends in wave energy technology development. While patents indicate technological progress, bibliometric analysis of academic publications captures research activity, identifies knowledge gaps, and maps scientific advancements.

The findings in this study indicate that wave energy research is expanding, even as patent registrations decline. This suggests that the area remains in an R&D phase, rather than at commercial maturity. Publishing and patenting share novelty and industrial applicability requirements, yet open-access mandates of both strategies, may lead companies to adopt trade secrecy as an alternative IP protection strategy.

Furthermore, academic institutions are at the forefront of wave energy technology research, benefitting from institutional and funding agency financial support, while patenting faces financial barriers. Having financial support for patent protection will help companies to attract investment.

Geographic trends highlight different innovation strategies, with China, UK, US, Italy, Spain, and Ireland leading in research publications, whereas the UK, USA, Sweden, Germany, and Finland dominate patenting registrations for the same period. This divergence mirrors national variations in commercialisation and IP policies.

Ultimately, patents should be assessed alongside other innovation indicators. Future research should examine how patenting and publishing trends shape commercialisation, management strategy, and policy in the wave energy sector.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Energy Agency, "Net zero by 2050," 2020, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/net-zero-by-2050>
- [2] F. O. Rourke, F. Boyle, and A. Reynolds, "Renewable energy resources and technologies applicable to Ireland," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2009.
- [3] M. E. McCormick, *Ocean Wave Energy Conversion*. Courier Corporation, 2013.
- [4] B. Guo and J. V. Ringwood, "A review of wave energy technology from a research and commercial perspective," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 15, pp. 3065–3090, 2021.
- [5] Government of Ireland, "Climate action and low carbon development act 2021," 2021, <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie>.
- [6] C. Barry and J. Ringwood, "Navigating funding challenges in the pursuit of wave energy technology development," in *Proceedings of 6th International Conference on Renewable Energies Offshore, Lisbon*, 2024.
- [7] World Intellectual Property Office, "Rd, innovation and patents," 2024, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: [R&D, Innovation and Patents](https://www.wipo.int/ip/innovationandpatents)
- [8] the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the European Patent Office (EPO) and the International Centre for Trade and Sustainable Development (ICTSD), "Patents and clean energy: bridging the gap between evidence and policy," 2010, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unclearn.org/wp-content/uploads/library/unep96.pdf>
- [9] International Renewable Energy Agency, "Off-shore wind energy patent insight report," 2023, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.irena.org/Publications/2023/Nov/IRENA-EPO-Offshore-Wind-Energy-Patent-Insight-Report>
- [10] World Intellectual Property Office, "Mapping innovations: Patents and the sustainable development goals," 2024, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wipo.int/web/patent-analytics/mapping-innovations-patents-sustainable-development-goals>
- [11] I. P. O. of Ireland, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ipoi.gov.ie/en/>
- [12] C. Buckner, "Machine for utilizing and storing the power produced by the rise and fall of the waves (us138474a)," 1973.
- [13] Government of Ireland, "Patents act 1992," 1992, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1992/act/1/enacted/en/html>
- [14] The Law Review, "Law review," 2010, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://thelawreviews.co.uk/title/the-patent-litigation-law-review/ireland>
- [15] A. Kleinknecht and G. van der Panne, "The propensity to patent an innovation: comparing entrepreneurial with routinized innovators," *Handbook of Research on Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, p. 439, 2011.
- [16] The United Nations, "The paris agreement," 2015, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement>
- [17] "SIEMENS GAMESA RENEWABLE ENERGY AS v. General Electric Co." 2022.
- [18] International Renewable Energy Agency, "Wave energy technology brief," 2014, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.irena.org/publications/2014/Jun/Wave-energy>
- [19] Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland, "Offshore renewable energy technology roadmap executive summary," 2024, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.seai.ie/publications/Executive-Summary-ORE-Roadmap.pdf>
- [20] M. M. Crossan and M. Apaydin, "A multi-dimensional framework of organizational innovation: A systematic review of the literature," *Journal of Management Studies*, 2010.
- [21] C. G. Smith, "Design competition in young industries: an integrative perspective," *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 1996.
- [22] S. J. Kline and N. Rosenberg, "An overview of innovation," *Studies on Science and the Innovation Process: Selected Works of Nathan Rosenberg*, 2010.
- [23] The Guardian Newspaper, "Mysterious factory break-in raises suspicions about chinese," 2012, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/oct/10/mysterious-factory-break-in-raises-suspicions-about-chinese-visit>
- [24] —, "Guardian newspaper article," 2016, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/nov/01/>
- [25] "Siemens gamesa renewable energy a/s v ge energy uk limited and others," 2022.
- [26] A. Contigiani, D. H. Hsu, and I. Barankay, "Trade secrets and innovation: Evidence from the "inevitable disclosure" doctrine," *Strategic Management Journal*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2921–2942, 2018.
- [27] European Commission, "Intellectual property protection action plan," 2020, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/strategy/intellectual-property_en\#IP2020
- [28] B. Kroposki, R. Margolis, and D. Ton, "Harnessing the sun," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, 2009.

- [29] J. J. Cordes, H. Hertzfeld, and N. S. Vonortas, *Survey of high technology firms*. Office of Advocacy, US Small Business Administration Washington DC, 1999.
- [30] D. Crass, F. Garcia Valero, F. Pitton, and C. Rammer, "Protecting innovation through patents and trade secrets: Evidence for firms with a single innovation," *International Journal of the Economics of Business*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 117–156, 2019.
- [31] A. Kleinknecht and H. J. Reinders, "How good are patents as innovation indicators? evidence from German CIS data," *Innovation and growth: From R&D strategies of innovating firms to economy-wide technological change*, 2012.
- [32] EU Commission, "Clean energy technology observatory report, 2022," 2022, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/publications-and-documents/clean-energy-technology-observatory/ceto-reports-2022_en
- [33] International Renewable Energy Agency, "Irena (2024) inspire platform," 2024, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.irena.org/INSPIRE>
- [34] European Patent Office, "Ptstat database," last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.epo.org/en/searching-for-patents/business/patstat>
- [35] IEA, EPO, "Patents and the energy transition," 2021, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/patents-and-the-energytransition>, accessed
- [36] S. Oberthür, *The New Climate Policies of the European Union: Internal Legislation and Climate Diplomacy*. Asp/Vubpress/Upa, 2010, no. 15.
- [37] M. Pazhouhan, A. Karimi Mazraeshahi, M. Jahanbakht, K. Rezanejad, and M. H. Rohban, "Wave and tidal energy: A patent landscape study," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 2024.
- [38] N. Donthu, S. Kumar, D. Mukherjee, N. Pandey, and W. M. Lim, "How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines," *Journal of Business Research*, 2021.
- [39] Elsevier, "Scopus," last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/>
- [40] A. K. Klevorick, R. C. Levin, R. R. Nelson, and S. G. Winter, "On the sources and significance of interindustry differences in technological opportunities," *Research Policy*, 1995.
- [41] CorPwer Ocean, "Corpower ocean," 2025, <https://corpweroc.com/wave-energy-technology/>.
- [42] A. O'Hagan, C. Huertas, J. O'Callaghan, and D. Greaves, "Wave energy in europe: Views on experiences and progress to date," *International Journal of Marine Energy*, 2016.
- [43] P. B. Maurseth and R. Svensson, "The importance of tacit knowledge: Dynamic inventor activity in the commercialization phase," *Research Policy*, 2020.
- [44] G. Pisano, "Profiting from innovation and the intellectual property revolution," *Research Policy*, 2006.
- [45] D. J. Teece, "Profiting from technological innovation: Implications for integration, collaboration, licensing and public policy," *Research Policy*, 1986.
- [46] New York Times, "Texas instruments is sued by bowmar," 1974, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/1974/12/04/archives/texas-instruments-inc-is-sued-by-bowmar.html>
- [47] C. A. Barry and J. V. Ringwood, "Wave energy technology development in Ireland: employing the triple helix model of innovation for pragmatic policy interventions," *Technology in Society*, p. 102872, 2025.
- [48] E. Mansfield, "Academic research and industrial innovation," *Research Policy*, 1991.
- [49] D. Sumanadasa, "Protecting and promoting clean energy innovation through the trade secrets regime: Issues and implications," *Intellectual Property and Clean Energy: The Paris Agreement and Climate Justice*, pp. 399–424, 2018.
- [50] United Nations, "United nations framework convention on climate change," 1994, last accessed 21st March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://unfccc.int/>